

Efficiency and Electrical Properties of a Copper-Indium-Diselenide Photovoltaic Module under Real Operating Conditions

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Abstract

This work presents the outdoor testing of a Copper-Indium-Diselenide (CIS) module under real operating conditions, and a semi-empirical model for calculating the efficiency under all relevant operating conditions including varying cell temperature, solar irradiance and relative air mass. Six different models were tried for 1168 measured data sets. The best model contains six correlation parameters in a product of two terms. One term describes the behaviour of the module with decreasing irradiance (part-load behaviour), the other one the temperature and air mass impact. In order to assess the quality of the model, transformation methods were applied, allowing two-dimensional representations of measured data and the calculated efficiency. The model is a highly useful tool to determine accurately the annual output of CIS modules at different sites with known climate data which is indispensable for the calculation of electricity production costs. The model also provides the Standard Test Condition (STC) efficiency of 11.6% and its temperature coefficient of minus 0.050%/°C, before degradation. Both values are important for peak power estimation in system design. The efficiency of 11.6% is remarkably high. Empirical models were also developed for the open circuit voltage and short circuit current.

Keywords

Photovoltaics
CIS-module
Efficiency
Climatic impact

Introduction

Silicon is used as a semiconductor in most of the solar cell modules currently available. Monocrystalline and polycrystalline Si-modules achieve high efficiencies, 15 to 22%, but they are expensive to manufacture. Thin film Si-modules have the potential to become considerably cheaper, but they, so far, achieve efficiencies of only 5 to 9%. The semiconductor material copper-indium-diselenide, CIS, and its related compound copper-indium-gallium-diselenide, $\text{CuIn}_{1-x}\text{Ga}_x\text{Se}_2$ or CIGS, seem to offer promise for a new thin film technology [1, 2]. Recently new lab records of 20.4 % and 20.8 % respectively were achieved:

<http://www.empa.ch/plugin/template/empa/1/131438/---/l=2>.

<http://www.zsw-bw.de/en/support/news/news-detail/zsw-stellt-weltrekord-solarzelleher.html>.

The purpose of this paper is to investigate the behaviour of a CIS module under real

operating conditions. Reliable information about the different climatic impacts on the efficiency and output power of this promising kind of module is indispensable for the accurate prediction of monthly and annual electricity yield. This, in turn is required to calculate the cost of electricity production. A new semi-empirical model is presented in order to calculate the efficiency, and from that, the electrical output. A calculation procedure to obtain a prediction of the annual electricity yield based on a meteorological database has been presented in a previous paper [3]. This procedure can be used for different module types at different sites in order to select the module with the best cost-benefit ratio for photovoltaic systems.

Outdoor Testing

The selected CIS test sample was a ST40 module made by the former SIEMENS Solar, Germany (33cm x 129cm). It was bought on the open market and was randomly selected out of a batch of about 500 modules. For testing, the module was fixed on a sun-tracker. Current/voltage (I/V) characteristics for this module were acquired under different climatic conditions, providing efficiencies at varying ambient and cell temperatures, irradiancies and air masses. A typical I/V characteristic is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Typical current/voltage characteristic for a SIEMENS ST40 CIS module.

Fig. 1 shows 249 I/V data points, measured at an irradiance of approximately 1000 W/m^2 and an air mass of about 1.5. Ambient temperature was 25°C and wind speed around 13 km/h , resulting in a cell temperature of 45°C . These conditions provided a cell efficiency of 10.45% . This is surprisingly high, as compared to silicon thin film cells.

At one of the test days, 105 I/V-scans were taken at constant irradiance and air mass but varying cell temperature. Fig. 2 shows the result of the measurements. This kind

of test is used to obtain the efficiency as function of cell temperature, from which the temperature coefficient of efficiency is then determined.

Fig. 2: Efficiency vs. cell temperature at constant irradiance G_n and air mass AM.

Efficiency Model

The results of all I/V scans were used to derive a semi-empirical model, giving the cell efficiency η as a function of global irradiance G_n (impinging vertically onto the module), cell temperature ϑ and air mass AM. The best model was found to be:

$$\eta = p[qG_n/G_{no} + (G_n/G_{no})^m][1 + r\vartheta/\vartheta_o + sAM/AM_o + (AM/AM_o)^u] \quad (1)$$

The model takes into account that the efficiency, for physical reasons, is zero at zero irradiance. It also takes into account the linear efficiency decrease with temperature, shown in Fig 2. Furthermore non-linear air mass dependence is assumed, as expected from theoretical considerations. The parameters p , q , m , r , s and u in model (1) were determined using non-linear least squares fitting techniques. The numerical values of the parameters were found to be:

$$p = 18.55 \quad q = -0.3288 \quad m = 0.2612 \quad r = -0.1004 \quad s = -0.9678 \quad u = 0.9864 \quad (2)$$

In eq. (1) the following standard values are used for irradiance, cell temperature and air mass:

$$G_{no} = 1000 \text{ Wm}^{-2} \quad \vartheta_o = 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \quad AM_o = 1.5 \quad (3)$$

By using eq. (1) and the parameters (2), together with the standard values (3), the

efficiency η can be calculated for any operating state of the module.

Comparison of Measured Efficiencies with Model

Comparisons of the measured efficiencies with efficiencies calculated from model (1) are prepared by transforming the measured efficiencies to constant climatic condition values. The general transformation equations were published in [4]. The following relations (4) to (6) between the measured efficiencies η_m and the transformed efficiency measurements η_{m,x_0,y_0} are obtained by applying these transformation equations to (1):

$$\eta_{m,1000,1.5} = \eta_m - p[qG_n/G_{no} + (G_n/G_{no})^m][1 + r\vartheta/\vartheta_0 + sAM/AM_0 + (AM/AM_0)^u] + p[q+1][2 + r\vartheta/\vartheta_0 + s] \quad (4)$$

$$\eta_{m,25,1.5} = \eta_m - p[qG_n/G_{no} + (G_n/G_{no})^m][1 + r\vartheta/\vartheta_0 + sAM/AM_0 + (AM/AM_0)^u] + p[qG_n/G_{no} + (G_n/G_{no})^m][2 + r + s] \quad (5)$$

$$\eta_{m,1000,25} = \eta_m - p[qG_n/G_{no} + (G_n/G_{no})^m][1 + r\vartheta/\vartheta_0 + sAM/AM_0 + (AM/AM_0)^u] + p(q+1)[1 + r + sAM/AM_0 + (AM/AM_0)^u] \quad (6)$$

Equation (4) converts an efficiency value measured at irradiance G_n , cell temperature ϑ and air mass AM to the corresponding value at G_{no} and AM_0 but at measured cell temperature ϑ . Equation (5) transforms efficiency values measured at irradiance G_n , cell temperature ϑ and air mass AM to the corresponding values at ϑ_0 and AM_0 but at measured irradiance G_n . Finally eq. (6) transforms efficiency values measured at irradiance G_n , cell temperature ϑ and air mass AM to the corresponding value at G_{no} and ϑ_0 but measured air mass AM .

From model (1), the efficiency at $G_n = G_{no}$ and $AM = AM_0$ but varying cell temperature ϑ is found to be:

$$\eta_{1000,1.5} = p(q+1)(2 + s + r\vartheta/\vartheta_0) \quad (7)$$

Corresponding relationships are found for $\vartheta = \vartheta_0$ and $AM = AM_0$ but varying G_n , as well as for $G_n = G_{no}$ and $\vartheta = \vartheta_0$ but varying AM :

$$\eta_{25,1.5} = p[qG_n/G_{no} + (G_n/G_{no})^m](2 + r + s) \quad (8)$$

$$\eta_{1000,25} = p(q+1)[1 + r + sAM/AM_0 + (AM/AM_0)^u] \quad (9)$$

The Standard Test Condition (STC) efficiency and temperature coefficient of efficiency at STC are obtained from model (1) and the parameters (2) as follows:

$$\eta_{STC} = p(q+1)(2 + r + s) = 11.60 \% \quad (10)$$

$$\alpha_{STC} = (\partial\eta/\partial\vartheta)_{STC} = p(q+1)r/\vartheta_0 = -0.050 \%/^{\circ}C \quad (11)$$

By applying eqs. (4), (5) and (6) to all 1168 measured points (η , G_n , ϑ , AM), and taking into account the model results (7), (8) and (9), the comparisons shown in Figs. 3, 4 and 5 are obtained. They allow the model to be validated against the measured data.

Fig. 3: Efficiency vs. temperature at constant irradiance and constant air mass.

Fig. 4: Efficiency vs. irradiance at constant cell temperature and constant air mass.

Fig. 5: Efficiency vs. air mass at constant irradiance and constant cell temperature.

Figs. 3, 4, and 5 show good agreement between the efficiency model and the transformed measurements. The efficiency decreases linearly with cell temperature, Fig. 3. However, the decrease of -0.050 percentage points/ $^\circ\text{C}$ is less pronounced than with monocrystalline silicon modules e.g. $-0.062 \text{ } \%/^\circ\text{C}$ of the SIEMENS Solar's SM110-module [4], making the CIS module an attractive candidate for warm climatic conditions. Part-load efficiency, as shown in Fig. 4, is much better than for a CIGS module tested previously [3, 5], leading to higher efficiencies at low irradiancies. This is important at those sites that have low irradiance for most of the operating time. In contrast to tandem and triple junction modules [4,6], the efficiency of CIS modules do not decrease with increasing air mass, i.e. the red shift in the solar spectrum in the late afternoon, Fig 5. This was to be expected, because of the relatively low bandgap energy of 1.04 eV [7] in the CIS p/n junction. As expected for a low band-gap cell, the efficiency is lowest under air mass zero, Fig. 5. Favourable temperature, part-load and air mass behaviour make the CIS module an efficient solution, and probably also a cost-effective choice for a wide range of future applications.

Open Circuit Voltage

From the definition of the cell efficiency and on the assumption that the maximum power point(mpp)-current is proportional to the irradiance, at constant cell temperature and at constant air mass, it is concluded that the mpp-voltage is proportional to the cell efficiency. This means that the efficiency model (1) can also be used to model the mpp-voltage. From our measurements it was further found, that the open circuit voltage U_{oc} is to a good approximation proportional to the mpp-voltage, meaning that U_{oc} is fairly well proportional to the cell efficiency. However, it is evident that U_{oc} is independent on air mass, since all solar spectra contain photons with energies higher than the band-gap energy of the CIS-semiconductor material of about 1 eV [7]. This means that even at red-shifted solar spectra, the open circuit

voltage equals to that one at noontime, same cell temperature presumed. Furthermore we found empirically that the dependence of U_{oc} on irradiance, at constant cell temperature, can be represented well by the term $(G_n/G_{no})^n$. Taking all this into account, we obtain the model for U_{oc} to be:

$$U_{oc} = p_1(G_n/G_{no})^n [1 + r_1 \vartheta / \vartheta_0] \quad (12)$$

The parameters were found to be: $p_1 = 25.56 \text{ V}$ $n = 0.0689$ $r_1 = -0.0777$

From this we obtain the open circuit voltage under standard test conditions:

$$U_{oc,STC} = p_1(1+r_1) = 23.6 \text{ V} \quad (13)$$

The temperature coefficient of U_{oc} of the module, containing forty-two seriesconnected individual cells, is found to be:

$$\beta_{STC} = (\partial U_{oc} / \partial \vartheta)_{STC} = p_1 r_1 / \vartheta_0 = -0.079 \text{ V/}^\circ\text{C} \quad (14)$$

Equation (14) leads to the temperature coefficient of U_{oc} for one single CIS-cell, amounting to $-1.88 \text{ mV/}^\circ\text{C}$. As expected from the temperature coefficient of the efficiency, α_{STC} , equation (11), the temperature coefficient of the open circuit voltage, β_{STC} , (taken as absolute value) is slightly smaller than that one of monocrystalline silicon solar cells.

By applying transformation techniques equivalent to the equations (4) to (6), comparisons between model (12) and measured data are obtained. They allow the model (12) to be validated against the measured data in a two-dimensional manner. The results show the effect of irradiance and temperature on the open circuit voltage U_{oc} of the CIS module in question, Figs. 6 and 7.

Fig. 6: Open circuit voltage vs. irradiance at constant cell temperature

Fig. 7: Open circuit voltage vs. temperature at constant irradiance.

Fig. 6 shows an almost linear dependence of open circuit voltage over a wide range of irradiance, at constant cell temperature. However, at further reduction of irradiance, the voltage is, as expected, asymptotically falling down to the voltage zero. Also, as expected, the open circuit voltage decreases linearly with cell temperature at constant irradiance.

Short Circuit Current

It is evident that the short circuit current, I_{sc} , at high air masses must decrease with further increasing air mass, at constant irradiance and constant cell temperature, since the number of photons with energies higher than the band-gap energy of CIS decreases with the red-shifting solar spectrum in the late afternoon. On the other hand the same holds for the blue-shifting spectrum in the late morning hours approaching noon time, since the photons become too energy-rich and therefore only a fraction of that energy is converted into current. From this it is concluded that I_{sc} reaches a maximum value at a certain value of the air mass. This is in contrast to the commonly assumed independence of I_{sc} from the air mass. From our measurements we found that the short circuit current I_{sc} is to a good approximation proportional to the mpp-current. Taking additionally into account the definition of the cell efficiency and above considerations regarding the mpp- and open-circuit voltage, it is found that I_{sc} must depend on irradiance, cell temperature as well as on the air mass. Furthermore it is concluded that I_{sc} can be modelled in a similar way to the efficiency model (1). However, from extended regression analyses it was found that at constant irradiance and air mass, I_{sc} shows a weak non-linearity with regard to the cell temperature. Taking into account all these considerations, the best model for I_{sc} was found to be:

$$I_{sc} = p_2(G_n/G_{no})^i [1 + r_2\vartheta/\vartheta_0 + (\vartheta/\vartheta_0)^j + s_2AM/AM_0 + (AM/AM_0)^k] \quad (15)$$

The parameters were found to be:

$$p_2 = 2.319 \quad i = 1.007 \quad r_2 = -0.9346 \quad j = 0.9647 \quad s_2 = -0.9102 \quad k = 0.9592$$

From this we obtain the short circuit current under standard test conditions:

$$I_{sc,STC} = p_2(3 + r_2 + s_2) = 2.68 \text{ A} \quad (16)$$

The temperature coefficient of I_{sc} of the CIS-module is found to be:

$$\gamma_{STC} = (\partial I_{sc} / \partial \vartheta)_{STC} = p_2(r_2 + j) / \vartheta_0 = 0.00279 \text{ A/}^\circ\text{C} \quad (17)$$

As expected and found e.g. with silicon cells, the short circuit current increases slightly with increasing cell temperature, at constant irradiance and constant air mass. Furthermore a very weak non-linearity with respect to the irradiance is found.

Applying again transformation techniques equivalent to the equations (4) to (6), comparisons between model (15) and measured data are obtained. They allow the model (15) to be validated against the measured data in a two-dimensional manner. As an example the influence of air mass, AM, on the short circuit current, I_{sc} , at constant irradiance and cell temperature is shown in Fig. 8. A maximum short circuit of 2.79 A is found at an air mass of 5.4.

Fig. 8: Short circuit current vs. air mass at constant irradiance and cell temperature.

Discussion/Conclusions

Modelling and evaluation of about 1200 current/voltage (I/V) scans taken under real operating conditions from an ex factory CIS module ST40 from SIEMENS Solar showed a Standard Test Condition (STC) efficiency of 11.60 %, corresponding to a STC output of 42.4 W. The latter value is higher than that specified by the manufacturer (40W). The reasons for this unexpected behaviour are not yet known. Further clarification is required on these matters. Measurements would have to be taken on other modules of the same batch, in prime condition, and after defined periods of outdoor operation, in order to answer these questions. The STC efficiency of 11.60 % is remarkably high compared with other thin film modules [4].

At a cell temperature of 25°C and air mass of 1.5, a maximum efficiency value of

12.0 % at an irradiance of about 650 W/m^2 was found, Fig. 4. This indicates that the series resistance losses become significant at higher irradiancies. Improvement of the transparent conducting oxide (TCO) electrode on the front side of the cells might lead to a higher output at high irradiancies, which is, when the production of electricity is of most interest in many cases. At low irradiancies, the CIS module behaves considerably better than the CIGS module investigated in [3].

The absolute temperature coefficient of efficiency was found to be $0.050\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$. This value is somewhat lower than that for monocrystalline silicon cells, but it is much higher than that for amorphous thin film silicon cells [4]. This potentially makes the module a better candidate than monocrystalline silicon cells for warm climate applications.

Efficiency is almost constant with increasing air mass, i.e. red shift in the solar spectrum in the late afternoon. This tendency was also observed in an earlier study on a CIGS module [5]. From this, it is concluded that overall efficiency might possibly be increased further through increasing the band gap energy of the semiconductor material slightly by changing its chemical composition. There was no observable degradation of the module (decrease of efficiency with operating time) within the short time covered by this investigation. Measurements taken after one and/or more years of outdoor exposure might prove instructive.

Models have been developed for the open circuit voltage and short circuit current. As expected from basic considerations, the short circuit current, I_{sc} shows a maximum value with respect to air mass, at constant irradiation and temperature.

A more fundamental modelling of CIS efficiency is found in [8]. However, the authors present a practical module design tool, to explore the influence of various physical parameters, e.g. the influence of the ZnO resistivity and interconnect contact resistivity. In contrast to the model presented here, their model does not take into account climatic impacts on the efficiency. Modelling and the model parameters according to the present work for other modules than CIS, are found in [9, 10].

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